

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECT OF Z-THREADED CARBON NANOFIBERS ON THE IMPROVEMENT OF FLEXURAL PROPERTIES OF CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER LAMINATES USING THE 3-POINT BENDING TEST

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ABSTRACT

As a next generation composite material, carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) has great potential to be widely used in manufacturing industries due to its outstanding mechanical properties. The high strength to weight ratio, and high stiffness inherent to CFRPs make them a desired material in various kinds of applications. CFRPs frequently experience bending loads while in use for such things as aircraft, automobiles, bridges, etc. Anisotropic behavior and limited in through thickness properties are major concerns which affect the performance of CFRPs. Moreover, in the interlaminar region, traditional CFRPs are often vulnerable to matrix sensitive damage such as compressive failure, delamination, and shear failure due to the absence of enough strength in through thickness direction. The tensile and compressive stress generated by the bending loads can weaken the interlaminar shear properties due to the absence of fibers in through thickness and ultimately can lead to catastrophic failure. This study introduces a novel approach with z-threaded CFRP (ZT-CFRP), which incorporates electrically aligned z-threaded carbon nanofibers (CNFs) as reinforcement. Flexural test using 3-point bending was performed on both control CFRP and ZT-CFRP samples reinforced with 1.0 wt.% carbon nanofiber z-threads. The results showed a 15% improvement in the flexural strength and about 36% linear elastic range increase for the ZT-CFRP laminates compared to the unmodified CFRP laminates, and validated the effectiveness of nanofiber Z-threading strategy in strengthening composite materials against flexural loading.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials are quietly revolutionizing every field of engineering, offering designers new possibilities that often go unnoticed [1]. Composite materials are quietly revolutionizing every field of engineering, offering designers new possibilities that often go unnoticed [1]. Composites are highly desirable for primary and secondary structures in both military and civilian aircraft, bio engineering, sports, automobile, marine industry due to their combination of high stiffness, high strength, and low density [2-9].

Carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP) stands out among fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites due to its exceptional properties. CFRPs are widely adopted in engineering applications where weight savings and mechanical performance are critical. It offers notably higher tensile strength, modulus of elasticity, and fatigue resistance compared to other FRPs. In addition, CFRP demonstrates excellent performance under harsh conditions, with superior resistance to fire and chemical exposure [10].

Fig 1: Typical configuration of carbon fiber reinforced polymer

CFRP exhibits desirable properties along the fiber direction; however, its material properties are significantly limited in the through-thickness direction due to the absence of reinforcing fibers as shown in Fig 1. This leads to delamination, which occurs from interlaminar stresses combined with low through-thickness strength of the material. Since the fibers within the laminate plane do not reinforce the through-thickness direction, this phenomenon arises [11]. Additionally, conventional CFRPs are prone to damage that is sensitive to the matrix, including issues like compressive failure, delamination, and shear failure in the interlaminar areas, primarily due to the lack of strength in the z-direction. The lack of reinforcement in this direction results in delamination when subjected to significant out-of-plane loads [12]. The tensile and compressive stress generated by the bending loads can weaken the interlaminar shear properties due to the absence of fibers in through-thickness and ultimately can lead to catastrophic failure

Several approaches have been explored for through-thickness reinforcement to enhance delamination resistance across the thickness. The most widely studied techniques include nanoparticle reinforcement [13-15] and stitching [16-17]. Although fiber stitching improves the interlaminar properties of CFRPs, boosting resistance to delamination and damage, it also presents challenges, such as potential fiber damage by the stitching machine and process, greater manufacturing complexity, and a reduction in overall performance for certain applications.

Watson et al. [18] used graphene oxide (GO) to improve the flexural properties of CFRP but incorporating GO into the composite has had minimal impact. Zhou et al. [19] found higher flexural properties by using nanoclay in CFRP composite. But high nanoclay content increases composite stiffness but reduces flexibility and energy absorption, leading to early failure under flexural stress. It also limits resin chain mobility, hindering effective stress redistribution [20]. Ulus et al. [21] also achieved higher flexural properties by using boron nitride nano particles and carbon nano tube.

This study aims to investigate flexural properties as well as observe failure mechanisms and microstructural changes that occur in the patented [22] CNF z-threaded CFRP (ZT-CFRP) after deformation in comparison to traditional CFRP. Three point bending test in accordance with ASTM D-790 will be performed to obtain the flexural properties of ZT-CFRP. As illustrated in Fig 2, in a ZT-

CFRP the zig-zag pattern of carbon nanofibers threading between carbon fiber array in the z-direction forms an interlocked multiscale fiber reinforcement network which increases the interlaminar shear properties as well as other mechanical properties such as interlaminar shear strength, in-plane shear strength, and longitudinal compressive strengths [23-26]. The z-threaded carbon fiber reinforced polymer (ZT-CFRP) laminates, due to its advanced nano-structured reinforcement network, have been shown to have strengthened mechanical [23-26], thermal [26, 27], and electrical [28] properties.

Fig 2: Principle behind the ZT- CFRP system

3 EXPERIMENTATIONS

3.1 Materials

The materials used to perform this experiment were: Hexcel AS4 unidirectional fabric (1.79 g/cm³ fiber density, 12k tow size), Epon 862 epoxy resin and Epikure-W curing agent (Miller-Stephenson Chemical Co. Inc.), CNF PR-24-XT-PS grade (Pyrograph Products Inc.), S-191 and S-192 surfactants from BYK. Unmodified control CFRP and 1.0 wt.% ZT-CFRP were prepared in this study.

3.2 Control CFRP prepreg manufacturing

To fabricate the control CFRP, Epon-862 epoxy resin was combined with Epikure-W curing agent at a weight ratio of 100:26.5 and mixed manually. The resulting mixture underwent a 90-minute degassing process in a vacuum oven set at 120 °C. Throughout degassing, the resin was periodically monitored for B-staging every 2 to 5 minutes starting at the 45-minute mark. Once degassed, the resin blend was processed into a thin, uniform film using a proprietary film-casting technique. This film was then segmented into smaller portions and stored at -17 °C to preserve its pre-cure state for subsequent prepregging. These frozen segments were later reheated to 120 °C and subjected to hot-melt processing, during which they were impregnated into AS4 carbon fiber using a patent-pending [29] roll-to-roll ZT-CFRP prepreg manufacturing machine.

3.3 ZT-CFRP prepreg manufacturing

In the preparation of ZT-CFRP, 1.0 wt.% of CNFs were mixed with Epon-862 epoxy resin. In ZT-CFRP, achieving a uniform dispersion of carbon nanofibers (CNFs) throughout the resin blend is crucial. If not properly dispersed, the CNFs can coagulate in localized areas, compromising the material's performance. To ensure distribution, in resin mixture containing CNFs, 1 wt.% of surfactants Disperbyk-191 and Disperbyk-192 were added. This step is essential for maintaining the homogeneity of the mixture and optimizing the properties of the final CFRP product. For proper mixing, the mixture was

mixed with high shear mixture for 60 minutes in clockwise and anticlockwise directions on an equal time. After the CNFs were incorporated into the matrix, the mixture underwent mechanical mixing for one hour followed by one hour of sonication using a QSONICA Q700 sonicator until proper dispersion of CNFs was found in microscope.

Fig 3 : Depiction of the concept of ZT-CFRP prepreg production process: (a) a thin hot-melt film consisting of B-staged resin/CNFs mixture with Epikure-w (b) Unaligned CNFs under the electric field (c) aligned resin/CNFs mixture in the cooled and solidified thin film (d) flow transfer aligned CNFs/resin mixture with carbon fiber into dry carbon fabric using a non-isothermal hot-melt ZT-CFRP prepreg manufacturing system (e) stacking of prepreps for laminate curing (f) cured ZT-CFRP laminate

The resin mixture was initially placed in a vacuum chamber at 120 °C for 60 minutes to remove entrapped air and volatiles. Following this initial degassing, the curing agent Epikure-W was added to the epoxy resin at a stoichiometric ratio of 100:26.5 and manually mixed to ensure homogeneity. The blended solution was then subjected to a second degassing and partial curing (B-staging) process at 100 °C for 90 minutes. B-staging progress was monitored starting at the 45-minute mark, with assessments performed every 2 to 5 minutes.

For the fabrication of ZT-CFRP prepreps, the CNF/epoxy resin film was immediately passed through an applied electric field, which oriented the carbon nanofibers into a continuous, aligned structure. As the film cooled, the resin matrix solidified, preserving the nanofiber alignment within the film. The aligned CNF/epoxy film was subsequently sectioned into specified dimensions and stored at -17 °C to maintain its pre-cure state.

These CNF-aligned resin films were fed to the proprietary ZT-CFRP prepreg machine (patent-pending [29]) to impregnate an unidirectional carbon fabric containing many fiber tows and output the ZT-CFRP prepreg at the end of the machine. The final prepreg sheets, containing uniformly aligned CNFs, were again stored at -17 °C until further use in composite fabrication.

3.4 Out-of-Autoclave–Vacuum Bag Only Process for Curing Composite Laminate

Fig 4: Schematic Diagram of OOA-VBO (Autoclave vacuum bag only) Setup.

In the Out-of-Autoclave–Vacuum Bag Only (OOA-VBO) process, an aluminum mold surface was first treated with a release agent, carefully avoiding regions designated for bonding with the sealant tape. The layup sequence included a peel ply layer, stacked CFRP plies, a second peel ply, a vacuum channel, sealant tape, and a vacuum bag, as illustrated in Fig 4. The assembly was placed in a hot press and cured at 120 °C for 120 minutes. After curing, the panel was allowed to cool under vacuum before demolding. A subsequent post-cure at 180 °C for another 120 minutes was performed to enhance the laminate's thermal and mechanical stability. This controlled process facilitates the production of high-quality CFRP laminates with aligned CNF-reinforced prepregs, ensuring optimal mechanical performance and structural consistency.

3.5 Flexural Test

Fig 5: Experimental Setup for 3 Point Bending Test

The samples were tested using the universal testing machine (Tinius Olsen 60SL) at a constant crosshead displacement rate of 4.0 mm/sec (see Fig 5). The laminate CFRP samples were tested to evaluate their flexural bending response following ASTM D790-03 [30]. The specimens were measured 100 mm Length x 20 mm Width x 2.30 mm Thickness. The Span length was 75 mm.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The flexural stress-strain curves until failure are plotted in Fig 6 for both control CFRP and ZT-CFRP and stress, strain and movement of the cross head were calculated according to ASTM D790. The average flexural stress for control CFRP was 1067 MPa while 1228 MPa for ZT-CFRP showing 15% higher strength. This enhanced in-plane shear performance indicates that the CNF z-threads reinforce the layers by forming an interlocked multiscale fiber reinforcement network in both the interlaminar zone and intralaminar zone to achieve overall reinforcing effect between carbon fibers in the laminate.

Fig 6: Stress strain curve for control CFRP and ZT-CFRP

In the three-point bending test, the control CFRP exhibited higher deflection compared to the ZT-CFRP, indicating that it is more flexible and less stiff, especially after it passed the elastic deformation range with the flexural strain ranging from 0-0.55% (i.e., the straight line range of the stress-strain curves). This greater deflection suggests that the control sample has lower resistance to bending after the elastic range, potentially due to weaker fiber–matrix interactions or lower structural reinforcement leading to the micro-level internal damages such as micro-cracks prior the total failure of the laminate. In contrast, the reduced deflection observed in the ZT-CFRP implies improved elastic performance along with extended elastic range with the flexural strain ranging from 0-0.75% (i.e., the straight line range of the stress-strain curves), likely resulting from enhanced mechanical interlocking through the CNF z-threads and carbon fibers network. The stress–strain curve of ZT-CFRP displays a significantly well-defined initial slope as a straight line compared to the control’s bending down curve, indicating a more predictable and linear elastic behavior of ZT-CFRP. This is followed by a well-defined plastic deformation phase and a subsequent drop in stress after failure. Such a profile is indicative of ductile material behavior, characterized by the ability to sustain considerable deformation and absorb energy before fracturing. On the other hand, the control CFRP exhibited a gradual decline in strength accompanied by higher deflection, which is indicative of limited load-bearing capacity and reduced

structural integrity after the much earlier initial failure (as indicated by the much smaller linear elastic strain range up to only 0.55% strain) compared with ZT-CFRP (with significantly larger linear elastic strain range up to only 0.75% strain). This behavior suggests that control CFRP has a weaker reinforcement mechanism, with less energy absorption and lower resistance to crack propagation compared to ZT-CFRP. Furthermore, all five ZT-CFRP specimens showed significantly more consistent and reliable flexural performance than the five control CFRP specimens, which indicated the ZT-CFRP likely provided a more reliable reinforcement system than control CFRP, at least for bearing flexural loading. Table 1 summarizes the flexural properties of control and ZT-CFRPs.

Table 1: Flexural properties of control and ZT-CFRPs

CFRPs	Fiber Volume Fraction (%)	Avg. Force (N)	Avg. Flexural Strength (MPa)	Max. Linear Elastic Strain (%)	Max. Linear Elastic Stress (MPa)
Control CFRP	53	1076	1067	~0.55	~800
1.0 wt.% ZT-CFRP	52	1230	1228	~0.75	~1228
Improvement of ZT-CFRP	-	-	+15.1%	+36.4%	+53.5%

Fig 7: Fracture mode of control CFRP (top) and ZT-CFRP (bottom)

In control CFRP samples, interlaminar cracks tend to follow a smooth, well-defined path, indicating weak interface adhesion and a propensity for resin-dominated failure (Fig. 7). This clean separation

between layers suggests limited resistance to crack propagation across the laminate. In contrast, the ZT-CFRP exhibits a highly irregular and disrupted crack path. This behavior is attributed to the presence of carbon nanofiber (CNF) z-threads, which enhance mechanical interlocking between layers. These z-threads act as barriers to crack growth, diverting and arresting crack propagation. In some instances, the improved bonding and load transfer facilitated by the z-threads are so effective that the failure progresses through fiber breakage rather than just matrix or interface failure, highlighting a significant improvement in structural integrity and damage tolerance.

Fig 8 : Microscopic images of the control CFRP (left) and ZT-CFRP (right) at 100x magnification show distinct fracture patterns. The control CFRP exhibits a straight fracture path, while the ZT-CFRP displays a curved fracture trajectory accompanied with separation of carbon fibers.

Microscopic side-view images (see Fig 8) of ZT-CFRP reveal that the aligned carbon nanofibers (CNFs) serve as reinforcement bridges between adjacent fiber layers. These nanofibers effectively bear compressive stresses in the top layer, enhancing structural integrity. Top-view images (see Fig 9) further demonstrate that the CNFs form interlocking connections between carbon fibers, strengthening the bonding and providing support under tensile stresses in the bottom layer. This suggests that the z-threaded CNFs act as anchoring elements, resisting delamination within individual layers by holding carbon fibers together. Additionally, the reinforced bonding created by these z-threads between stacked layers is strong enough to prevent tearing or propagation of cracks into neighboring layers.

Fig 9 : Top-side microscopic images of the control CFRP (left) and ZT-CFRP (right), captured at 1000x and 1250x magnification, highlight significant microstructural differences between the two materials. The control CFRP surface appears relatively smooth and featureless at this scale, whereas the ZT-CFRP clearly exhibits an interlocked network of nanofibers.

Fig 10: Presence of carbon aligned z-threaded nanofibers in through-thickness between the adjacent layers of carbon fibers.

As shown in Fig 10, the presence of carbon-aligned Z-threaded nanofibers in the through-thickness direction between adjacent carbon fiber layers significantly enhances interlaminar load transfer, improves fiber–matrix adhesion, and contributes to superior structural integrity and delamination resistance. These observations strongly support the hypothesis that enhancing interlaminar and

intralaminar load transfer through the incorporation of nanofiber z-threads not only improves fiber–matrix adhesion but also significantly contributes to the overall structural integrity of the composite under flexural bending. This improved interlaminar and intralaminar performance helps to inhibit crack propagation and increases resistance to delamination, thereby enhancing the mechanical performance of the laminate under various loading conditions including the flexural test in this study and other reported properties such as ILSS [23, 26], inplane shear strength [24], and longitudinal compressive strength [25].

5 CONCLUSIONS

Flexural properties are crucial because they directly influence how laminated CFRP panels bend, fail, and behave when subjected to bending loading. The incorporation of 1.0 wt% z-threaded CNFs into CFRP resulted in an average increase of 15% flexural strength compared to the control CFRP. The CNF interlocking networks within the ZT-CFRP prepreg significantly strengthened the intralaminar region and also contributed to a moderate enhancement in the interlaminar region. The ZT-CFRP exhibited large linear elastic range with strain ranging of 0-0.75% compared with the range with 0-0.55% of the control CFRP. The combined results showed a 15% improvement in the flexural strength and about 36% linear elastic range increase for the ZT-CFRP laminates compared to the unmodified CFRP laminates, and validated the effectiveness of nanofiber Z-threading strategy in strengthening composite materials against flexural loading. In conclusion, the ZT-CFRP specimens were found to be more linearly predictable, more reliable, and stronger than control CFRP for bearing flexural loading.

In future work, the authors intend to introduce thin carbon nanotube (CNT) interleaves between the ZT-CFRP prepreg to further strengthen the interlaminar region. This future interleaf modification on ZT-CFRP is expected to enhance the laminate's overall matrix-sensitive properties. Additionally, conducting numerical simulations of ZT-CFRP could provide valuable insights into the composite's complex behavior at the microscale, helping to better understand and optimize its mechanical performance,

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